

TRANSIENT ELASTIC WAVES PROPAGATING IN A COMPOSITE LAYERED MEDIUM FOR DYNAMIC LOADINGS

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SUMMARY: The propagation of elastic transient waves in a multi-layered medium subjected to in-plane loadings is investigated in this study. One of the objectives of this study is to develop an effective analytical method for determining transient full field solutions in the layered medium. The connection between the proposed matrix method and the generalized ray method is established for the layered medium in the transform domain. The matrix representation of solution enables us to calculate the transient response of the layered medium without tracing the ray path manually. An experimental setup that simulates the plane stress condition for a layered half space is established to obtain the dynamic displacement response and the result agrees with the theoretical solution very well.

KEYWORDS: transient wave, dynamic loading, layered medium, matrix expansion.

INTRODUCTION

The applications of composite materials have grown very rapidly for the last two decades because of their high strength and light weight. The methods to find the response of composite laminates under various conditions have appeared to be of most significant concern in this field. The capability of composite materials to transmit impact loads is often the critical feature of design. For static analysis, this has already received widespread attention in the last two decades. However, the study of transient response has started to grow in recent years. Hence, the characterization and methodology for studying wave propagation in composite materials is of prime interest. Analytical investigation of the layered composite medium subjected to impact loading has been meagre because the transient analysis involves numerous parameters and is enormously complex. Only few researches used the transient analysis to study wave propagation in a multilayered solid.

Spencer [1] proposed the method of generalized ray to obviate the necessity for solving the tedious boundary value problem by constructing the solution from the application of the results of simpler problems. The method leads to an infinite series of the generalized ray integral constructed in the Laplace transform domain by assembling the source function, reflection and transmission coefficient, the receiver function and the phase function. The inverse of the ray integral is found in a closed form by applying the Cagniard method

(Cagniard, [2]). Since the transient response for the layered medium is exact up to the arrival time of the next ray, only finite number of rays is involved in the early time solution. The theory of generalized ray was cast to determine the transient response of a plate by Ceranoglu and Pao [3], a multilayered medium by Müller [4]-[5], and was reviewed by Pao and Gajewski [6]. For the long time response at a receiver in the layered medium, however, the difficulty arises in determining a large number of generalized ray paths along which the rays arrived at the receiver. As a degenerated case, the transient responses of a thick plate were studied in a great detail by Pao and his coworkers [6] through the utilization of the generalized ray method. The transient waves generated by a buried compressional pulse in a two-layered solid (a layer overlaying a half-space) were calculated theoretically and numerically by Abramovici and Alterman [7] and Alterman and Karal [8], respectively. This work was based on the numerical evaluation of the exact solution and the analysis was extremely involved and time consuming.

In this paper we will show how the generalized ray solutions for a multilayered medium can be constructed directly by attacking the corresponding boundary value problems with aids of the integral transform technique and the matrix Bromwich expansion. By rearranging the coefficient matrix in a special form consisting of the diagonal, lower triangle and upper triangle parts and extracting the diagonal part from it, and then the matrix Bromwich expansion is applied to obtain the global phase-related reflection and transmission matrix which characterizes the multiple reflections and transmissions of all waves in each and every layer. This approach leads itself to ray interpretation. The transient response is obtained by the application of Cagniard's method for Laplace inversion. With aids of the proposed method, the phase function which is determined manually in the theory of generalized ray, is determined automatically by the phase related matrices and vectors. The surface motions of a layer overlying a half-space are measured experimentally, and are compared with the theoretical calculation. The good agreements between experimental and theoretical waveforms imply the accuracy of numerical calculation and the possible application of the result to the detection of perfect bonding condition.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Consider an initially undisturbed multilayered medium consisting of n layers separated by parallel planes as depicted in Fig. 1. Each layer is assumed homogeneous and isotropic, and discontinuity condition is considered at the interfaces. Since responses for the medium subjected to dynamic loadings which are located within layers can be obtained by introducing artificial interfaces at the applied-loading locations, hence we consider first that all applied loadings are located at interfacial or lateral surfaces of the multilayered medium. The boundary conditions on top and bottom layers of the medium can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_{yy}^{(1)}(x,0,t) &= \sigma_{yy}^{[0]}(x,t) \\
 \sigma_{xy}^{(1)}(x,0,t) &= \sigma_{xy}^{[0]}(x,t) \\
 \sigma_{yy}^{(n)}(x,-h_n,t) &= \sigma_{yy}^{[n]}(x,t) \\
 \sigma_{xy}^{(n)}(x,-h_n,t) &= \sigma_{xy}^{[n]}(x,t)
 \end{aligned}
 \quad \text{for } -\infty < x < \infty, \tag{1}$$

where

$$h_n = \sum_{i=1}^n h^{(i)},$$

in which $h^{(i)}$ is the thickness of the i th layer. Loadings applied at the interface $y = -h_i$

between two adjacent layers yield the traction and displacement discontinuity conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} u^{(i)}(x, -h_i, t) - u^{(i+1)}(x, -h_i, t) &= u^{[i]}(x, t) \\ v^{(i)}(x, -h_i, t) - v^{(i+1)}(x, -h_i, t) &= v^{[i]}(x, t), \\ \sigma_{yy}^{(i)}(x, -h_i, t) - \sigma_{yy}^{(i+1)}(x, -h_i, t) &= \sigma_{yy}^{[i]}(x, t) \\ \sigma_{xy}^{(i)}(x, -h_i, t) - \sigma_{xy}^{(i+1)}(x, -h_i, t) &= \sigma_{xy}^{[i]}(x, t), \end{aligned} \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1, \quad (2)$$

We define an applied displacement-traction vector $\mathbf{t}^{[i]}$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, n$) at the $n+1$ planes to simplify our expression,

$$\mathbf{t}^{[0]} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{yy}^{[0]} & \sigma_{xy}^{[0]} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{t}^{[n]} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{yy}^{[n]} & \sigma_{xy}^{[n]} \end{pmatrix},$$

and

$$\mathbf{t}^{[i]} = \begin{pmatrix} u^{[i]} & v^{[i]} & \sigma_{yy}^{[i]} & \sigma_{xy}^{[i]} \end{pmatrix}^T, \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1. \quad (3)$$

If there is no discontinuity at the interface i , the applied displacement-traction vector at this interface should vanish, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{t}^{[i]} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}^T. \quad (4a)$$

When a concentrated vertical force is applied at the interface, the discontinuity is given by

$$\mathbf{t}^{[i]} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -f(t)\delta(x) & 0 \end{pmatrix}^T. \quad (4b)$$

The discontinuity caused by a concentrated horizontal force is then

$$\mathbf{t}^{[i]} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -f(t)\delta(x) \end{pmatrix}^T. \quad (4c)$$

For a glide edge dislocation or a horizontal slip fault suddenly generated at time $t = 0$ along the interface i , the problem can be represented by assuming (Boore *et al.*, [9])

$$\mathbf{t}^{[i]} = \begin{pmatrix} -bH(t)H(x) & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}^T, \quad (4d)$$

where b denotes the magnitude of Berger's vector. The solutions for various types of dynamic loadings can be obtained by a linear superposition.

FORMULATIONS IN DOUBLE TRANSFORM DOMAIN

In absence of body forces, the two-dimensional equations of motion expressed in terms of two displacement potentials ϕ and ψ are

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} = s_L^2 \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2}, \quad (5a)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} = s_T^2 \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2}, \quad (5b)$$

where

$$s_L = \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\lambda + 2\mu}} = \frac{1}{c_L}, \quad s_T = \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\mu}} = \frac{1}{c_T}.$$

Here ρ is the mass density of the material; λ and μ are elastic constants of Lamé; s_L and s_T are slownesses of longitudinal and transverse waves, respectively. Displacement components are given in terms of two potentials by

$$u = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y}, \quad (6a)$$

$$v = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, \quad (6b)$$

where u and v are the displacements in the x and y direction, respectively. On invoking Hooke's law and Eq.(6), the stress components are

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{xx} &= \mu \left((s_T^2 - 2s_L^2) \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2} + 2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x \partial y} \right) \right), \\ \sigma_{yy} &= \mu \left((s_T^2 - 2s_L^2) \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2} + 2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x \partial y} \right) \right), \\ \sigma_{xy} &= \mu \left(2 \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} \right).\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

The definition of a function $f(x, y, t)$ in the double Laplace transform domain is given by

$$\hat{f}(y; \xi, p) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-p\xi x} \int_0^{\infty} f(x, y, t) e^{-pt} dt dx, \quad (8a)$$

The inverse formulation is given by

$$f(x, y, t) = \frac{-P}{4\pi^2} \int_{\xi_1 - \infty i}^{\xi_1 + \infty i} e^{p\xi x} \int_{p_1 - \infty i}^{p_1 + \infty i} \hat{f}(y; \xi, p) e^{pt} dp d\xi. \quad (8b)$$

By applying the double Laplace transform according to the definition given by Eq.(8a), Eqs.(5a) and (5b) become two ordinary differential equations with the following general solutions,

$$\hat{\phi}(y; \xi, p) = \phi_-(\xi, p) e^{+p\gamma_L y} + \phi_+(\xi, p) e^{-p\gamma_L y}, \quad (9a)$$

$$\hat{\psi}(y; \xi, p) = \psi_-(\xi, p) e^{+p\gamma_T y} + \psi_+(\xi, p) e^{-p\gamma_T y}, \quad (9b)$$

where $\gamma_L = \sqrt{s_L^2 - \xi^2}$, and $\gamma_T = \sqrt{s_T^2 - \xi^2}$. The unknown functions ϕ_- , ψ_- , ϕ_+ and ψ_+ are four field coefficients of each layer, to be determined by boundary conditions. For convenience, we arrange the field coefficients in Eq.(9) into two column matrices,

$$\mathbf{c}_- = (\phi_- \quad \psi_-)^T, \quad (10a)$$

and

$$\mathbf{c}_+ = (\phi_+ \quad \psi_+)^T, \quad (10b)$$

for downgoing and upgoing waves, respectively. From Eqs.(6) and (7) and introducing the displacement vector $\mathbf{u} = (\hat{u} \quad \hat{v})^T$ and traction vector $\mathbf{f} = (\hat{\sigma}_{yy} \quad \hat{\sigma}_{xy})^T$, the displacement-traction vector and field coefficient matrices in transform domain are related as follows,

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{u}(y) \\ \mathbf{f}(y) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{11}(y) & \mathbf{M}_{12}(y) \\ \mathbf{M}_{21}(y) & \mathbf{M}_{22}(y) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{c}_- \\ \mathbf{c}_+ \end{pmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$\mathbf{M}_{11}(y) = p \begin{bmatrix} \xi e^{-p\gamma_L y} & \gamma_T e^{-p\gamma_T y} \\ \gamma_L e^{-p\gamma_L y} & -\xi e^{-p\gamma_T y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12a)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{12}(y) = p \begin{bmatrix} \xi e^{p\gamma_L y} & -\gamma_T e^{p\gamma_T y} \\ -\gamma_L e^{p\gamma_L y} & -\xi e^{p\gamma_T y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12b)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{21}(y) = \mu p^2 \begin{bmatrix} (s_T^2 - 2\xi^2) e^{-p\gamma_L y} & -2\xi\gamma_T e^{-p\gamma_T y} \\ 2\xi\gamma_L e^{-p\gamma_L y} & (s_T^2 - 2\xi^2) e^{-p\gamma_T y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12c)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{22}(y) = \mu p^2 \begin{bmatrix} (s_T^2 - 2\xi^2) e^{p\gamma_L y} & +2\xi\gamma_T e^{p\gamma_T y} \\ -2\xi\gamma_L e^{p\gamma_L y} & (s_T^2 - 2\xi^2) e^{p\gamma_T y} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12d)$$

$$\mathbf{U}_i = \begin{pmatrix} -\mathbf{M}_{12}^{(i+1)}(-h_i) & \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 2} \\ -\mathbf{M}_{22}^{(i+1)}(-h_i) & \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 2} \end{pmatrix}, (i = 1, 2, \dots, n-2)$$

$$\mathbf{U}_{n-1} = \begin{pmatrix} -\mathbf{M}_{12}^{(n)}(-h_{n-1}) \\ -\mathbf{M}_{22}^{(n)}(-h_{n-1}) \end{pmatrix}; \quad (19)$$

and the nonzero blocks for lower triangular matrix \mathbf{L} is defined as

$$\mathbf{L}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{11}^{(1)}(-h_1) \\ \mathbf{M}_{21}^{(1)}(-h_1) \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{L}_i = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 2} & \mathbf{M}_{11}^{(i)}(-h_i) \\ \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 2} & \mathbf{M}_{21}^{(i)}(-h_i) \end{pmatrix}, (i = 2, 3, \dots, n-1)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_n = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 2} & \mathbf{M}_{21}^{(n)}(-h_n) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

It is noted that the diagonal block matrix \mathbf{D} is a nonsingular matrix. The stacked matrix equation can be solved directly by

$$\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{M}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{t}}. \quad (21)$$

By arranging the response functions in each layer into a response vector, we can relate this vector to the globe field vector with a phase-related receiver matrix \mathbf{R}_{cv} . For example, if the response functions for u , v , σ_{yy} and σ_{xy} in each layer are concerned, we should define the response vector as

$$\hat{\mathbf{b}}(y; \xi, p) = \begin{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}^{(1)}(y) \\ \hat{v}^{(1)}(y) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{yy}^{(1)}(y) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{xy}^{(1)}(y) \end{pmatrix}^T & \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}^{(2)}(y) \\ \hat{v}^{(2)}(y) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{yy}^{(2)}(y) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{xy}^{(2)}(y) \end{pmatrix}^T & \dots & \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}^{(n-1)}(y) \\ \hat{v}^{(n-1)}(y) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{yy}^{(n-1)}(y) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{xy}^{(n-1)}(y) \end{pmatrix}^T & \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}^{(n)}(y) \\ \hat{v}^{(n)}(y) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{yy}^{(n)}(y) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{xy}^{(n)}(y) \end{pmatrix}^T \end{pmatrix}^T. \quad (22)$$

Thus the global field vector is related to the response vector by

$$\hat{\mathbf{b}}(y; \xi, p) = \mathbf{R}_{\text{cv}}(y) \mathbf{M}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{t}}, \quad (23)$$

where the global phase-related receiver matrix is given by, in views of Eq.(12),

$$\mathbf{R}_{\text{cv}}(y) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{11}^{(1)}(y) & \mathbf{M}_{12}^{(1)}(y) & & & \\ \mathbf{M}_{21}^{(1)}(y) & \mathbf{M}_{22}^{(1)}(y) & & & \\ & & \mathbf{M}_{11}^{(2)}(y) & \mathbf{M}_{12}^{(2)}(y) & \\ & & \mathbf{M}_{21}^{(2)}(y) & \mathbf{M}_{22}^{(2)}(y) & \\ & & & & \ddots \\ & & & & & \mathbf{M}_{11}^{(n)}(y) & \mathbf{M}_{12}^{(n)}(y) \\ & & & & & \mathbf{M}_{21}^{(n)}(y) & \mathbf{M}_{22}^{(n)}(y) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (24)$$

We rewrite the coefficient matrix \mathbf{M} in an alternative form by extracting the diagonal block matrix \mathbf{D} out of the expression

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{R}), \quad (25)$$

where the expression of \mathbf{R} matrix is given by

$$\mathbf{R} = -\mathbf{D}^{-1}(\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{U}), \quad (26)$$

or alternatively,

The densities and the elastic constants of the brass, stainless steel, aluminum and acrylic thin plates are given as follows,

Table 2: Material constants of the specimens

Material	$\rho(kg/m^3)$	$E(GPa)$	ν	$c_L(m/s)$	$c_T(m/s)$
Brass	8600	1100	0.34	4437	2184
Stainless steel	7850	207	0.29	5878	3197
Aluminum	2700	70	0.33	6197	3121
Acrylic	1190	6.32	0.32	2717	1426

The concentrated force applied on the top surface of the medium with an approximate step source time function which can be generated by the breakage of pencil leads. The source time function shown in Fig. 3 is obtained by breaking the pencil lead directly on the NBS conical transducer. The source time function generated by the breakage of pencil leads has a short arising time about $1\mu s$ and is reproducible without damage the sample. Note that the source time function received by the transducer decays exponentially when time increases. The exponential decay is caused by the dynamic characteristic of the NBS conical transducer. However, we can find a function to fit the source time function as follows,

$$f(t) = e^{-\omega t} \left(1 - (1 - \beta t^2) e^{-\gamma t^2} \cos \chi t \right) H(t), \quad (32)$$

To check the bonding effects by using epoxy resin, we prepare a specimen which is composed of two aluminum plates with dimension listed at Table 1, specimen No. 1. If the specimen is bonded perfectly, the response should behave like a half space. The experimental results for specimens No. 1 and 5 as well as the numerical calculation are illustrated in Fig. 4. The good agreement between the experimental waveforms for specimens No. 1 and 5 implies that the bonding condition by epoxy resin is nearly perfect.

The experimental waveforms and the numerical calculations for the vertical displacements on the free surface of specimen No. 2 with a distance 3, 6, 9, and 12 *cm* away from the location of applied force are shown in Fig. 5. The numerical calculations based on the analytic solutions agree very well with the experimental waveforms in the early time responses. However, the numerical calculations fail to fit the experimental waveform at about $55\mu s$ since the reflected waves from the side edge which are not taken into account in the analytic model arrives at the receiver. For specimen No. 2, it is noted that the wave speed relations between the overlying layer and the half space are $c_{p(1)} > c_{p(2)} > c_{s(2)} > c_{(1)}$. The none dispersive property of Rayleigh surface wave can be identified in the figure.

Fig. 6 shows the experimental waveforms for the vertical displacements on the free surface of specimen No. 3. It is noted that the wave speed relations between the overlying layer and the half space are $c_{p(2)} > c_{p(1)} > c_{s(2)} > c_{(1)}$. The transient response of this specimen behaves like the surface vertical displacement for a half space. However, the surface response is smaller than that of the half space because of the support of the bed half-space.

Fig. 7 is the transient vertical displacement signal received at $x = 3cm$ away from the applied loading on the free surface of specimen No. 4. The numerical calculated and experimental measured results are in agreements at the early time response. The experimental measurement can not fit the numerical calculation well after the arrival of Rayleigh wave. It is possibly caused by the anelastic nature of acrylic and by the effect of the bonding layer. The numerical calculated time history of vertical displacement appear the nature of periodical oscillation with damping at almost a constant value.

CONCLUSIONS

A matrix method is proposed in this study to analyze transient waves in a multilayered medium subjected to inplane dynamic loadings. With aids of the matrix Bromwich expansion, we arranged the solution in the transform domain into a power series of the reflection and transmission matrix \mathbf{R} , each term representing a group of waves that are reflected by or transmitted through the interface the same times. The final solution in transform domain is a series composed of the product of the receiver matrix \mathbf{R}_{cv} , the power matrix of \mathbf{R} , and a source vector \mathbf{s} . The connection between the proposed method and the generalized ray method is established by considering the reflection and transmission of waves at a single interface. The numerical calculations for displacement based on the analytic results are compared with experimental measurements. Good agreements are obtained between the numerical calculated and experimental measured signals, which imply the feasibility of the application by utilizing transient elastic waves in the nondestructive evaluation of material properties.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of this research by the National Science Council (Republic of China) under Grant NSC 87-2212-E-002-035.

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Fig. 1. Configuration and coordinate system of an n-layered medium.

Fig. 2. The system of two dimensional acoustical emission experiment.

Fig. 3. The calibration experiment for pencil lead breaking source and NBS conical transducer.

Fig. 4. The control experiment for bonding condition.

Fig. 5. The comparison of measured and calculated waveforms on the free surface of specimen No. 2 (Dash lines for the experimental measurements; and solid lines for the numerical calculations).

Fig. 6. The comparison of measured and calculated waveforms on the free surface of specimen No. 3 (Dash lines for the experimental measurements; and solid lines for the numerical calculations)

Fig. 7 The comparison of measured and calculated waveforms on the free surface of specimen No. 4 (Dash lines for the experimental measurement; and solid line for the numerical calculation).